

NEW APPROACHES IN IMPROVING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS IN UZBEK EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: Uzbekistan's educational system faces a challenge: equipping students with the necessary English speaking skills for academic and professional success. Traditional grammar-heavy methods fall short of fostering fluency. This article explores innovative approaches to address this issue. It advocates for a communicative approach that prioritizes using English for real-world scenarios like debates, presentations, and project-based learning. Technology plays a key role with interactive learning apps, educational podcasts, and collaborative online platforms. Cultivating a culture of speaking English through designated areas, language exchange programs, and English clubs further enhances fluency. Teachers play a crucial role with professional development opportunities and collaborative teaching strategies. Finally, the article discusses effective assessment methods, including standardized tests, teacher observation rubrics, and self/peer assessment. By embracing these new approaches, Uzbek educational institutions can empower students to confidently communicate in English, preparing them for the globalized world.

Key words: Speaking skills, Uzbek educational institutions, communicative approach, task-based learning, project-based learning, language-learning apps, teacher professional development, collaborative teaching, speaking assessment, standardized tests.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida talabalarni akademik va kasbiy muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun ingliz tilida gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish asosiy omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Grammatikaga asoslangan an'anaviy usullar nutqiy ravonlikni rivojlantirishda ijobiy natijalar ko'rsatmaydi. Ushbu maqola muammoni hal qilish uchun innovatsion yondashuvlarni o'rganadi. U munozaralar, taqdimotlar va loyihaga asoslangan o'rganish kabi real ssenariylar uchun ingliz tilidan foydalanishga ustuvor ahamiyat beradigan kommunikativ yondashuvni yoqlaydi. Interfaol ta'lim ilovalari, ta'limga oid podkastlar va boshqa onlayn platformalar til o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Til almashish dasturlari va ingliz tili klublari orqali ingliz tilida gapirish madaniyatini rivojlantirish ravonlikni yanada oshiradi. O'qituvchilar kasbiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlari va hamkorlikda o'qitish strategiyalari bilan hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Bundan tashqari maqolada samarali baholash usullari,

jumladan standartlashtirilgan testlar, o'qituvchining kuzatish rubrikalari va o'z-o'zini / tengdoshlarini baholash muhokama qilinadi. O'zbekiston ta'lim muassasalari ushbu yangi yondashuvlarni qo'llash orqali talabalarga ingliz tilida ishonchli muloqot qilish imkonini beradi, ularni globallashtirgan dunyoga tayyorlaydi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalari, o'zbek ta'lim muassasalari, kommunikativ yondashuv, vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim, loyiha asosida o'qitish, til o'rganish ilovalari, o'qituvchining malakasini oshirish, hamkorlikda o'qitish, nutqni baholash, standartlashtirilgan testlar.

Аннотация: Перед системой образования Узбекистана стоит задача: обеспечить учащихся навыками разговорной речи на английском языке, необходимыми для академического и профессионального успеха. Традиционные методы, основанные на грамматике, не способствуют беглости речи. В данной статье рассматриваются инновационные подходы к решению этой проблемы. Он выступает за коммуникативный подход, который отдает приоритет использованию английского языка в реальных сценариях, таких как дебаты, презентации и обучение на основе проектов. Технологии играют ключевую роль в приложениях для интерактивного обучения, образовательных подкастах и онлайн-платформах для совместной работы. Развитие культуры разговорного английского в специально отведенных местах, программах языкового обмена и английских клубах еще больше повышает беглость речи. Учителя играют решающую роль, предоставляя возможности профессионального развития и стратегии совместного преподавания. Наконец, в статье обсуждаются эффективные методы оценки, включая стандартизированные тесты, критерии наблюдения учителя и самооценку/оценку сверстников. Приняв эти новые подходы, узбекские образовательные учреждения смогут дать учащимся возможность уверенно общаться на английском языке, готовя их к жизни в глобализованном мире.

Ключевые слова: разговорные навыки, узбекские образовательные учреждения, коммуникативный подход, обучение на основе задач, обучение на основе проектов, приложения для изучения языка, профессиональное развитие учителей, совместное обучение, оценка разговорной речи, стандартизированные тесты.

The ability to communicate effectively in English is essential for students' academic success and future careers in today's globalized world. However, traditional methods focused on grammar drills and rote memorization often fail to cultivate fluency. This article explores innovative approaches to enhance speaking skills in English in Uzbek educational institutions.

Shifting the Paradigm: From Grammar-Translation to Communication

For decades, the grammar-translation method dominated English language teaching in Uzbekistan. This approach emphasizes memorizing grammatical rules and translating texts between English and Uzbek. While essential to a certain extent, grammar drills can hinder spoken communication. New approaches advocate for a communicative approach that prioritizes using English for real-world communication. This method focuses on:

- **Real-World Scenarios:** Activities like debates, group presentations, role-playing exercises, and simulations encourage students to utilize English for everyday communication, fostering a dynamic and engaging learning environment.

- **Task-Based Learning:** This method centers on specific tasks that require students to use English to achieve a goal. Examples include planning events, conducting interviews, or creating presentations on historical figures.

- **Project-Based Learning:** Projects can be long-term endeavors where students research, collaborate, and present information entirely in English. This promotes deeper engagement and reinforces speaking skills.

Leveraging Technology for Personalized Learning

Technology offers exciting possibilities for improving spoken English:

- **Interactive Language Learning Apps:** Gamified apps with features like speech recognition, pronunciation feedback, and personalized language courses provide engaging practice opportunities outside the classroom. Popular options include Duolingo, Memrise, and English-specific apps like HelloTalk and Busuu.

- **Educational Podcasts and Online Resources:** Podcasts covering topics ranging from current events to English literature and history provide immersive listening experiences and expose students to authentic accents and speech patterns. Online documentaries, educational videos, and educational TV shows can also be valuable resources.

- **Collaborative Learning Platforms:** Online platforms like Google Classroom or Microsoft Teams allow students to record presentations, share documents, and participate in online discussions, all in English, fostering collaboration and practice.

Cultivating a Culture of Speaking in English

Creating an environment that encourages speaking English is crucial for fostering fluency. Here are some ways to achieve this:

- **English-Only Zones:** Designate specific areas in the school where only English is spoken. This can include common areas like the cafeteria or student lounges.

- **Language Exchange Programs:** Partner with schools in English-speaking countries to establish language exchange programs. This allows students to converse with native speakers and gain exposure to different dialects and cultural nuances.

• **English Clubs and Speaking Competitions:** Organize English clubs where students can engage in conversation practice, debates, or dramatic presentations. Hosting speaking competitions can motivate students to improve their fluency and public speaking skills.

Enhancing the Role of Teachers

Teachers play a pivotal role in fostering a positive and effective learning environment. Here are some ways to equip teachers for promoting speaking skills:

• **Professional Development:** Provide teachers with professional development opportunities to learn and implement new communicative language teaching methodologies. Workshops on using technology in the classroom, incorporating real-world scenarios, and task-based learning can be beneficial.

• **Collaborative Teaching:** Encourage collaboration among English teachers to share best practices and develop creative lesson plans that promote speaking skills.

• **Peer Observation:** Implement peer observation programs where teachers can observe each other's classes and provide constructive feedback on promoting speaking activities.

Assessment and Evaluation

Evaluating speaking skills effectively is essential to gauge progress and identify areas for improvement. Here are some methods for assessing speaking skills:

• **Standardized Speaking Tests:** Standardized tests like the TOEFL or IELTS can measure a student's overall English proficiency, including speaking skills.

• **Teacher Observation and Rubrics:** Teachers can use rubrics that assess various aspects of speaking skills, such as fluency, pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary use.

• **Self-Assessment and Peer Assessment:** Encourage students to self-assess their speaking skills and participate in peer assessment activities to identify strengths and weaknesses.

By embracing these new approaches, Uzbek educational institutions can empower students to develop effective communication skills in English, preparing them for academic success and future careers in an increasingly interconnected world. This article has explored various approaches to improve speaking skills in English in Uzbek educational institutions. It has emphasized the importance of shifting from grammar-translation methods to a communicative approach, leveraging technology for personalized learning, cultivating a culture of speaking English, enhancing the role of teachers, and implementing effective assessment practices. By adopting these strategies, Uzbek institutions can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment where students can develop fluency and confidence in using English for real-world communication.

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